

A scoping review assessing the impact of dissemination of public resources on the risks of sugar-sweetened beverages (SSBs) among adults in New York City

Abstract

Background

In the recent decade, several campaigns by the NYC Department of Health and Mental Hygiene targeting sugary predators have been launched in New York City (NYC) to address the dangers of consuming sugar-sweetened beverages (SSBs). With a significant amount of evidence correlating the link between SSB consumption and co-morbidities such as obesity and type-2 diabetes, new opportunities have been highlighted to address the rising epidemic. However, it remains unclear if the use of targeted public communication strategies and their effectiveness.

Methods

For the scoping review, one independent researcher reviewed the literature using three different search engines. Analyzing studies with relevant MeSH terms to determine the quality and relevancy. The PRISMA method was used as a guideline for screening and to aid visually in the selection process.

Results

A total of 56 (n=56) relevant studies in which relevant MeSH terms such as health communication, digital literacy, behavioral intervention, sugar, and adult health messaging were used to narrow the search. The PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram was used to depict the process of inclusion and exclusion to ensure the quality and replication of the review. A total of passed the second round of review (n=40).

Conclusions

Based on the scoping review, a media campaign is not sufficient to provide a significant change in the population size of New York City, as data suggests that the most significant change occurs at the individual level.

Introduction:

Studies suggest social mobility has been linked to health outcomes in public health. A higher income per capita correlates with better health outcomes and quality of life. New York City has demonstrated through evidence that income inequality runs rampant throughout the five boroughs, making the prevalence of obesity and type-2 diabetes higher in geographic areas with lower income per capita. The New York City Department of Health and Mental Hygiene (NYC DOHMH) has envisioned setting better outcomes and addressing health inequity across the city. Through promotional campaigning, the NYC DOHMH has launched a series of mixed-media campaigns to combat the consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages (SBB). Since 2013, the

NYC DOHMH has introduced a series of media advertisements that consist of a combination of digital advertisements and 15–30-second television advertisements to convey the dangers of sugary consumption. The NYC DOHMH, through its campaigning against the consumption of SSB, has adopted a community framework through its advertising to engage the population in behavioral change. With the overarching goal of ongoing evaluation, outreach, and communication within susceptible communities.

The current state of the field of mass mixed-media campaigns implements a similar framework that uses evaluation design, as it evaluates the audience and whether its advertising effects the individual, social, or institutional. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TBB), which was first introduced as an intervention to determine self-regulation through tactics of planned or modified conditioning, has been repeatedly used through advertising, especially for SBB consumption.

The idea of TBB is that one will act through perceived behavior and its norms. For the past decade, the NYC DOMH has focused on its messaging towards the individual and through their advertising, while using several tactics for their form of conditioning. In previous campaigns, the NYC DOMH provocatively used grotesque imagery to innately elicit a response among the individual. This technique aims to garner a response of “self-change” through an emotional response to the imagery.

Using this scoping review, this study identifies the effectiveness of public health communication and its intervention strategies. Outlining if the NYC DOHMH current model of advertising is the best intervention to convey the dangers of the consumption of SBB’s.

Methods

The scoping review consisted of guidance from previous well-established methods to determine how to set eligibility criteria and search methods. Utilizing three different search engines to conduct reviews was used to increase the conspicuousness of the available material. PubMed, Scopus, and the Cochrane Library were used to conduct the review.

Specifically for the search and review of available material in PubMed, the use of Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) was applied as a search strategy. This search strategy broadened the availability of relevant articles and narrowed the scope and areas of focus. A combination of search terms were used, including but not limited to digital communication, individual intervention, sweetened, advertising, and health messaging. These terms are used as a starting point to pull out relevant studies for further review.

PRISMA Method:

The PRISMA Method was used to evaluate studies that were pulled for further analysis. PRISMA is sourced as an evidence-based method to evaluate intervention through a four step process that includes identifying the article for review, screening, deciding for eligibility, and

finalizing the article for systematic review. The PRISMA offers a visual aid to organize the flow of the four-step process.

Articles that were eligible for further review were studies conducted after 2010, and participants were young-adult above the age of 18. A total of 56 (n=56) were pulled for further analysis. After determining eligibility for the second round of screening, a total of (n=40) were reviewed. Factors determining further analysis were either for record duplication or did not meet the standards of criteria that were previously set.

Figure 1

Results

When synthesizing the results of the review, there were four overarching themes that fit under the categories of individual perception, criticism of intuition, digital literacy, and challenges in demographics and cultural aculturation. Each category is specific to the previous review, and significant themes were repeatedly presented throughout the review. The category of individual perception delineated that the study had a major affect on the individual or was catered to alter the individual’s behavior. For a critique of the institution, it was outlined that societal factors such as income, race, and geographic location had a significant impact on the consumption of media and its relevant policies.

Digital literacy underlines the challenges and positive outcomes of incorporating digital tools in an advertising campaign. Also, highlight patterns of online behaviors that could be correlated to one's attitude and perceptions of health, either positively or negatively. With challenges in demographics, studies have highlighted how language can be a significant marker of improvement when utilized; however, it is often overlooked when determining the dosage of programming and advertising. **TABLE 1**

Summary	Theme
<u>Individual’s perceptions are influenced by packaging and brands marketing strategies.</u>	Individual Perception
<u>A five-week national campaign to reduce the consumption of junk food. The study highlighted that there is a significant link between increased knowledge with respondents less likely to purchase junk food that was advertised in a negative light.</u>	Individual Perception
<u>Food marketing campaigns are driven by patterns of human social norms. Successful campaigns are driven by addiction or habit.</u>	Individual Perception
<u>Campaign models and exposure seek to communicate messages to a specific audience. Transitioning messages to prompt a response, conversation, and prompt self-change.</u>	Individual Perception
<u>Socially charged counter-ads are mainly used to address policy-driven issues. Challenging personal opinions are used to promote “self-responsibility”.</u>	Critique to the Institution
<u>Social media has leverage to change public opinion on public-health issues.</u>	Digital Literacy
<u>Public Service Announcements are funneled to target a particular demographic for maximum impact.</u>	Challenges in Demographics and Cultural Aculturation
<u>Mass media interventions targeted at minorities in a population in large found little to no effect on self-reported behavioral change. The intervention was done over 3 months with television programming with media targeted in multiple languages.</u>	Challenges in Demographics and Cultural Aculturation
<u>The majority of studies found that there’s a significant pattern of adults commonly using Facebook, studies have found that there is a small but significant improvement when social media intervention is used.</u>	Digital Literacy
<u>Social media has leverage to change public opinion on public-health issues.</u>	Digital Literacy
<u>Online peer support has shown positive significance in behavioral health intervention.</u>	Digital Literacy
<u>Data-driven practices are needed to generate effective digital intervention. These results are generated from behavioral evaluation.</u>	Digital Literacy
<u>Advertising has measurable effects on individuals, altering emotional beliefs.</u>	Individual Perception
<u>Strategies for effective messaging include a processing desire for information and an attitude to promote action.</u>	Individual Perception
<u>Technology-based strategies may potentially promote engagement, however, still an emerging field to have a concrete answer.</u>	Digital Literacy
<u>False health claims can be highly persuasive, due to imagery and advertising.</u>	Individual Perception
<u>Food advertising has a strong effect on adults, there was a 45% increase in consumption with imaginary.</u>	Individual Perception

<u>Exposure to social media gratifies needs in adults and pressures individuals to act on certain behaviors.</u>	Digital Literacy
<u>Substantial evidence demonstrates that behavioral change could be implemented through web-based intervention.</u>	Digital Literacy
<u>Digital marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchase choice and brand image.</u>	Digital Literacy
<u>Lower levels of digital literacy are found in older populations, presenting challenges when consuming digital health interventions.</u>	Digital Literacy
<u>Structural inequities reinforce the digital inclusion of minority populations in the access to digital behavioral intervention.</u>	Critique to the Institution
<u>A digital framework to classify digital health interventions based on individual function, time, and facilitation.</u>	Digital Literacy
<u>Research suggests that campaign intervention which places a greater emphasis on long-term effects with a combination of frequent communication, allows for a higher impact.</u>	individual Perception
<u>Studies suggest multi-factor engagement for advertising effectiveness.</u>	individual Perception
<u>A conceptual framework is needed to further analyze metrics to determine the effectiveness of digital health campaigns.</u>	Digital Literacy
<u>Television advertising generated higher levels of campaign awareness.</u>	individual Perception
<u>Web behavioral patterns are helping in examining the dosage of health intervention.</u>	Digital Literacy
<u>Interactive engagement may have improved re-call comprehension.</u>	Digital Literacy
<u>Push for the necessity of policy reform of the implementation of higher taxes for sugar-sweetened beverages.</u>	Critique to the Institution
<u>Latino-based broadcast networks advertise fewer health-beneficial advertisements than English-based networks.</u>	Challenges in Demographics and Cultural Aculturation
<u>Spanish media remains popular for passive and active reach among Latino communities, research suggests that there is value in including more digital-based interventions to improve health promotion.</u>	Challenges in Demographics and Cultural Aculturation
<u>Research suggests that many culturally component forms of digital health intervention do not demonstrate a “downstream effect” in digital health intervention.</u>	Challenges in Demographics and Cultural Aculturation
<u>12-week tailored intervention highlighted had culturally appropriate materials show a significant impact on behavioral health outcomes.</u>	Challenges in Demographics and Cultural Aculturation
<u>Public relations opportunities could highlight opportunities for individual engagement.</u>	individual Perception

<u>Billboard advertising provides productive pathways to yield larger audiences when delivering behavioral health intervention.</u>	individual Perception
<u>Direct communication permits enlightening direct audiences.</u>	individual Perception
<u>Racialized marketing stems from structural forces of health inequity.</u>	Challenges in Demographics and Cultural Aculturation
<u>The higher average of SSB marketing during SNAP insurance days compared to other days of the month, exacerbating diet quality.</u>	Critique to the Institution
<u>Research suggests that ethnic minorities have higher exposure to SSB advertising due to outdoor food marketing and strategic placement.</u>	Critique to the Institution

Discussion

For findings, there was an overwhelming theme of exposure to a targeted behavioral intervention affecting a significant change in one's behavior. This individual perception could be affected by branding, imagery, and, more importantly, underlying beliefs. Research suggests that motivation is evident in one's decision to adopt a particular behavior. However, they are external influences; one's personal motivation is a constant.

An unexpected finding is how the dosage of a media campaign could significantly improve the outcome of behavioral change. For example, the duration of an advertisement on television or the length of the campaign. Highlighting that digital intervention that has a higher run time in access showed a higher chance for one's behavioral change.

This is significant in the case of the NYC DOHMH, as they have a slotted time of exposure for the public, such as in television programming for three months, compared to being available on other platforms such as YouTube and Facebook.

Limitations

One of the limitations for this scoping review is the use of one reviewer to conduct the findings. An other perspective would been helpful as different perspectives could understand data differently

The second limitation is that this scoping review is “less strict” for the exclusion criteria as there was only two categories for limitation, Narrowing the scope of the review the outcomes could have been more specific for each theme that was encountered.

Conclusions:

Based on the scoping review, a media campaign is not sufficient to provide a significant change in the population size of New York City, as data suggests that the most significant change occurs at the individual level. 44% of the studies highlighted that individual perceptions and personal motivators are key to behavioral change. However, it could be factored in when creating and evaluating a behavioral health intervention for communities. Such as adding elements for cultural competency and acknowledging the limitations each community faces with their population.

